

Una.Resin WP2 – Pilot Action Blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures

Report

Version 0.3

WP2 Team

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Introduction

The Blueprint provides relevant information to start developing a **common Una Europa digital catalogue of research infrastructures and a web portal of services**. The catalogue is intended as a dataset about the research infrastructures of Una Europa universities. The blueprint foresees the development of a platform that will include the basic information on the infrastructures and contact information on the infrastructure manager (or responsible researcher), but also further information, such as the research results produced through the use of the research infrastructure as well as functionalities and services such as booking and training.

The underlying **rationale** is the need expressed by the stakeholders to share information and knowledge on research infrastructures and resources available in Una Europa universities: the academic and professional community engaged during the implementation of Una.Resin confirmed that this is one of their expectations about Una Europa. Una Europa institutions are very large, comprehensive universities, and this makes it difficult to have a complete overview of infrastructures and expertise. A **key step for opening and sharing infrastructures and for establishing collaborations in R&I** is to be aware of the infrastructures and resources available in the universities of the Alliance. Having a common digital catalogue that will serve as a unified access point for information on Una Europa research infrastructures will stimulate information sharing and will ease cross-institutional access, fostering research collaborations. As highlighted in the “Shared Una Europa strategy for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources” (D2.2, see Pillar “Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration”) the development of common tools is a key step to facilitate cross-institutional access to the research infrastructures of the Alliance and their visibility, also towards external users including non-academic actors of the private and public sector and the civil society.

The main **benefits** of the catalogue can be summarized as follows: (i) increase awareness of the academic community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access to them; (ii) promote collaboration around RIs that can stimulate new collaborative research projects as well as an efficient use of RIs; (iii) connect RIs and promote Open Science principles in their operation and activities; (iv) promote the RIs towards possible non-academic public, private and third sector users and also towards citizens; (v) improve the economic sustainability of the infrastructure.

The content of the Blueprint is the result of the pilot action carried out by WP2 of Una.Resin project. A working group of IT experts of Una Europa institutions was created to undertake this pilot project: 14 participants from 8 Una Europa universities were involved and 4 discussion meetings were organized and held from December 2022 to May 2023, including a specific seminar to share best practices on RIs catalogues, involving also as guest the experts of the Flemish department Science, Economy and Innovation who designed the

Flanders Research Information Space ([FRIS](#)). The inputs emerged from the discussions held during the pilot action were collected and organized in different chapters of the Blueprint.

The first chapter focuses on **catalogues of infrastructures in the Una Europa universities** to report the current situation at Alliance level and designing the common catalogue starting from the resources already available at institutional level. The catalogues of Freie Universität Berlin, KU Leuven, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, University of Edinburgh and University of Helsinki are briefly described.

The second chapter is dedicated to the **best practices** of catalogues that involve two universities of the Alliance and an external stakeholder: FRIS - Flanders Research Information Space; the booking and accounting tool OpenIRIS at FUB and in the Berlin University Alliance (BUA); research infrastructure development at UH. The outcomes of the seminar offer a useful perspective and insights to design a common catalogue at trans-national level, and consider also the issues related to the number of partners and how this might impact on the management of the catalogue.

The third chapter reports the **lessons learned from the creation of a prototype** of the common catalogue. This experience has shown possible evolutions concerning the following points: (i) a possible extension of the data set with other attributes; (ii) a more accurate definition of the data model: which fields are mandatory, which ones are recommended, which ones are optional; (iii) the definition of a set of rules to ensure data quality for incoming data; (iv) the connection of the prototype data model to up-to-date data sources.

The fourth chapter is the core of the Blueprint: it contains the **technical features** suggested to implement the common catalogue. The catalogue is represented as a platform aimed at providing a unified system for managing data on RIs, enabling institutions to easily share information, thus fostering also the collaboration on research activities. The catalogue's design and features, along with the development process, are described in detail.

Chapter five contains suggestions for the universities that have not developed a catalogue at institutional level yet. Jagiellonian University, Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne and University of Bologna describe their current situation and future plans regarding the catalogue of research infrastructures. The Blueprint offers useful **recommendations for the development of an internal catalogue**: (i) identify the existing research infrastructures; (ii) classify them according to their function, research area/field; (iii) create a database listing the research infrastructures; (iv) adopt a standard for information on research infrastructures in the catalogue; (v) refer to a data model based on the CERIF standard.

The sixth chapter is aimed at **designing services** that can be added to the catalogue of research infrastructure. The proposed features and services are the following: (i) ensure the contact information of individuals requesting the access to RIs; (ii) link to registration system (to use the facility) in the RI digital catalogue; (iii) technical support; (iv) user training; (v) notifications and alerts system; (vi) link to an online catalogue of the research teams from Una Europa universities and their transferable research results; (vii) link between the RI

identifier and publication/data outputs achieved by using the RI: this would have positive impacts on the effective monitoring of scientific outputs and would allow to map the connection with infrastructure initiatives at different levels. An important recommendation stemming from the pilot is the development and use of a global Persistent identifier (PID) for research infrastructures.

The last chapter drafts the **next steps towards the creation of a common catalogue**. Based on a clear commitment of all Una Europa members and on a further exploration of experiences and best practices within and beyond the Alliance, an advanced blueprint (cf. D2.2) should be created, including: (i) in-depth SWOT analysis that can help the selection of architecture, system and taxonomy to be adopted in the common catalogue; (ii) definition of a detailed project and a budget for the development and management of the shared RIs catalogue (creation, updating, promotion, training); (iii) analysis of the potential financial risks associated with the project; (iii) definition of roles and responsibilities of the participating institutions; (iv) definition of processes that can ensure systematic updates of RI information through regular data collection to keep the information updated; (v) advanced indications for the development of further services and functionalities that will lead to the development of a common portal/platform.

From the technical point of view, it is important to specify that the catalogue is based on the process of **harvesting of existing information on Una Europa research infrastructures**. Starting from the information available at the institutional level, the catalogue foresees an automatic system to collect and display the existing data in a single place (web platform). This methodology is due to the need to decrease as much as possible the effort for the creation and the maintenance of the catalogue. For the universities that have not developed an internal catalogue of infrastructures yet, the Blueprint provides guidelines and indications on how to create it. A last point to consider is the interoperability of data. Some research infrastructures could be already included in catalogues at institutional or regional/national level. The development of the Alliance catalogue that was discussed by the experts would not conflict with other catalogues; in fact, it would allow data stored in the existing catalogues to be included at the same time also in the Una Europa catalogue. This approach can increase the use of data, thus positively affecting the use of research infrastructures and, in the long term, improving the quality of research in the universities.

It is worth reminding here that the Blueprint was prepared in the framework of WP2 “Research Infrastructures and Resources” of the Una Resin project, that aims to develop a strategy and action plan for sharing research infrastructures across Una Europa universities and start exploring concrete paths and sharing formats. The work is focused on the Focus Areas Cultural Heritage and One Health, but also with a connection to the other focus areas of the Alliance: Europe and the World, Sustainability, Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (AI), Future Materials.

In the first two years of the project, WP2 focused on a threefold mapping exercise¹ and on the consultation with stakeholders aimed to collect inputs and ideas for the Una Europa strategy and action plan for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (as part of the Una Europa R&I strategy). To this aim a co-creation workshop on research infrastructures was organized. Moreover, a joint workshop with the project RiTrainPlus was organized to develop synergies in the field of trainings for RIs managers. The last part of WP2 implementation foresees the development of two pilot actions aimed at exploring concrete formats to open up research infrastructures and resources: the development of a Blueprint for creating a common catalogue of RIs and the implementation of a matchmaking format targeted to RIs in the field of Cultural Heritage and One Health.

¹ (1) Benchmarking Una Europa member universities' RIRs strategies, policies, initiatives, including funding mechanisms, organisational and management models; (2) Mapping of the RIRs related to the challenge "Exploring cultural heritage to strengthen inclusion and participative communities"; (3) Mapping of the RIRs related to the challenge "Promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment"

1. Catalogues of infrastructures available in the Una Europa universities

The first step taken in designing a common catalogue of research infrastructures was the assessment of the catalogues already available at institutional level. Indeed, the intention was to build on the existing tools at the institutional level rather than to start from scratch. The universities that currently have a catalogue of infrastructures are the following: Freie Universität Berlin, KU Leuven, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, University of Edinburgh and University of Helsinki. Jagiellonian University, Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne and University of Bologna still do not have an operating catalogue. The main objectives and common points of the considered catalogues are:

- to improve the quality of research, enabling researchers to explore new areas of interest and to use cutting-edge tools, facilities and technologies;
- to foster interdisciplinary collaboration among researchers, improving the university's ability to tackle complex problems and create synergies between different disciplines;
- to make research infrastructures accessible to a wider audience, thus ensuring that research is inclusive;
- to attract excellent researchers and retain existing ones, improving the reputation and image of the university;
- to offer opportunities for advanced training and specialization for students and researchers in training;
- to attract more funding opportunities for research from external bodies.

The catalogues from Freie Universität Berlin, KU Leuven, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, University of Edinburgh and University of Helsinki are described below. Beyond the data regarding the description of the catalogues, the tables also show the technology of the datasets and the interoperability interface.

Freie Universität Berlin
Name of the digital catalogue tool of RIRs
BioSupraMol (BSM) Core Facility FU Berlin (Department of Biology, Chemistry, Pharmacy), SupraFab (SFAB) Research Building (Chemistry, Physics, Biology)
Web resource/web site URL
https://www.biosupramol.de/ https://www.suprafab.fu-berlin.de/
Management software, portal, data base or excel/access file where the information are stored

OpenIRIS; https://fub.openiris.io
Type of interoperability interface available to share the information outside the university (or instance Web APIs, JSON, CSV and flat file download)
Web, OpenIRIS
Note
OpenIRIS on the central level: No central level support currently provided

KU Leuven
Name of the digital catalogue tool of RIRs
Research portal – infrastructure
Web resource/web site URL
https://www.kuleuven.be/onderzoek/portaal/#/?hl=en&lang=en
Management software, portal, data base or excel/access file where the information are stored
Information about infrastructure is stored in SAP and is displayed on the KU Leuven research portal using Elastic Search
Type of interoperability interface available to share the information outside the university (or instance Web APIs, JSON, CSV and flat file download)
Public dataservice (API)
Note
<p>KU Leuven has a RIs catalogue as part of the research portal. RI items include infrastructures financed by funding programs specifically aimed at research infrastructure (internal KU Leuven funds, Funds of the Flemish Research Foundation). This information is put into the KU Leuven portal by the central research coordination office, not by the researchers themselves (but they can change information if they want) since this information is also delivered to Flanders Research Information Space (FRIS).</p> <p>Other infrastructures financed by different funds from other budgets (e.g. on research projects) can also be included but on request of the researcher. These RIR are not included in the FRIS RIR data set. Indeed, to proceed it is necessary to motivate researchers to provide sufficient information.</p> <p>Onderzoeksportaal (kuleuven.be) contains 9 key areas: (i) human health, (ii) medical technologies, (iii) matter, materials and energy, (iv) nature unlimited, (v) bio-sciences and environment, (vi) manufacturing and ICT, (vii) arts, religion and culture, (viii) economy, law and society; and (ix) human behaviour.</p>

Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Name of the digital catalogue tool of RIRs
Centros de Asistencia a la Investigación / Research assistance centres
Web resource/web site URL
https://cai.ucm.es/
Management software, portal, data base or excel/access file where the information are stored
Custom web development (Php + mySQL)
Type of interoperability interface available to share the information outside the university (or instance Web APIs, JSON, CSV and flat file download)
None currently. A tool could be developed to share the data in CSV format according to the requirements.
Note
NA

University of Edinburgh
Name of the digital catalogue tool of RIRs
NA
Web resource/web site URL
https://www.ed.ac.uk/medicine-vet-medicine/shared-research-facilities
Management software, portal, data base or excel/access file where the information are stored
Excel
Type of interoperability interface available to share the information outside the university (or instance Web APIs, JSON, CSV and flat file download)
None currently. A tool could be developed to share the data in CSV format according to the requirements.
Note
NA

University of Helsinki
Name of the digital catalogue tool of RIRs
TUHAT / Pure
Web resource/web site URL
https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/equipments/
Management software, portal, data base or excel/access file where the information are stored
Centralised systems: Pure system (CRIS), Equipment registry based on SAP LIMS RI management systems used in individual core facilities and RIs: LabVantage, Agilent ILab, openIRIS Web-based resources of individual RIs and faculties (UH www and intranet)
Type of interoperability interface available to share the information outside the university (or instance Web APIs, JSON, CSV and flat file download)
Different methods to access the Pure database
Note
TUHAT/Pure is the institutional centralized database for RI information, in addition individual RIs and faculties have their own web pages and other resources for storing and managing RI-specific information. These, however, are not managed centrally at present. In the near future, it will be integrated the SAP ERP ² equipment registry to TUHAT/Pure so that RIs and their relevant equipment can be linked in TUHAT. This greatly reduces the need to access different systems. TUHAT system also has a link to the national research.fi -portal (thus far not on RI information), future development includes data transfer of RI information from TUHAT to the national portal.

² SAP ERP is an enterprise resource planning software developed by the German company SAP SE.

2. Best practices

The second step made to collect useful inputs for designing a common catalogue of research infrastructures, is the assessment of best practices of initiatives in which the partner universities of Una.Resin are involved in. On the 21st of March 2023, the Una.Resin WP2 team organized the *Seminar on research infrastructures catalogues: best practices* with the aim to present the relevant experiences of RIs catalogues that involve the universities of the Una Europa. The development of the blueprint benefitted from the inputs and ideas that were discussed during the seminar. The best practices that were presented are the following: Flanders Research Information Space (FRIS); the booking and accounting tool OpenIRIS at FU Berlin and in the Berlin University Alliance (BUA); Research infrastructure development at University of Helsinki.

FRIS - Flanders Research Information Space

Description: FRIS is a current research information system (CRIS) and collects publicly funded research information implemented in Flanders. FRIS monitors research activities and monitors open science. FRIS is created to implement the following objectives:

- **openness:** to accelerate the chain from idea to innovation by ensuring a better information flow between research institutes and innovative organizations;
- **simplicity:** simply administration through webservices and obtaining information directly from systems and requesting information, sharing and reusing information;
- **effectiveness:** to make government, cooperate and research innovation strategy more effective and efficient;
- **transparency:** to make research information publicly available freely to all citizens.

In addition, FRIS maintains the following principles:

- data ownership³ by the research institutes;
- contact with the research institute (but not with individual researchers);
- take data input as it is and work in silos for the moment;
- plan to work for golden record-visualization⁴.

³ It was noted that data ownership may refer to research groups, which is subject to the national/regional context.

⁴ This means that in case when one unique infrastructure is used by different universities and data about this infrastructure are delivered by all universities separately, these data are grouped and re-oriented towards one unique input.

FRIS Research Portal, Infrastructure page⁵

Key elements emerged:

- automatic flow of connection to institutional systems and possibility of manual input;
- exchange format: CERIF standard based;
- high level of interoperability guaranteed by APIs;
- automated quality check;
- open access support.

The booking and accounting tool OpenIRIS at FU Berlin and in the Berlin University Alliance (BUA)

Description: OpenIRIS is a non-commercial, online hosted booking and management platform for academic, commercial and private customers. It is used for the booking and accounting of Multi-User-Devices in the Berlin University Alliance (Network of Freie

⁵ <https://www.ewi-vlaanderen.be/en/fris-flanders-research-information-space>

Universität Berlin, Technische Universität Berlin, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin and Charité Berlin).

The screenshot shows the FUB-IRIS Portal interface. At the top, there are navigation links for 'Resources', 'Providers', and 'Sign in / Register'. Below this is a search bar with 'Filter text' and a search icon. A filter menu on the left lists various resource categories with counts: ALL (38), ADMINISTRATION (1), ADMINISTRATION (BSM/SFAB - FU) (2), CALORIMETER (2), CENTRIFUGE (1), COATER (1), ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (7), GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS (1), HEATING (1), LAB SPACE (1), MASS SPECTROMETER (2), MASS SPECTROMETRY (1), OTHER INSTRUMENTS (1), PARTICLE SIZE ANALYZER (3), ROOM (7), and SPECTROMETER (4). The main content area displays a grid of resource cards. Each card includes an icon, a name, a provider, affiliations, and a resource type. Examples of resources include 'Add my group to FUB I...', 'Bruker D8 Venture', 'EnviroESCA', 'Fluorescence FL 6500', 'IONTOF M6', 'Kibron MicroTrough XS', 'bioMS measurements (...)', 'Circular Dichroism Spe...', 'FEI Vitrobot Mark IV (F...', 'Glovebox', 'IR Spectrum Two', and 'MicroCal PEAQ-ITC'.

FUB-IRIS Portal, List of resources⁶

Key elements emerged:

- common accounting software by different institutions;
- easy authentication via FU Berlin IT Single Sign On;
- resource booking service⁷;
- billing and statistics.

Research infrastructure development at University of Helsinki

Description: The most important central source of information describing the research infrastructures of the University of Helsinki is the infrastructure portal under the Research Portal database (<https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/equipments/>), which lists essential information on the University's research infrastructures on different campuses. Host units and, ultimately, those maintaining research infrastructures are responsible for submitting the

⁶ <https://fub.openiris.io/landing/resources/?searchText=&page=1>

⁷ <https://www.bcp.fu-berlin.de/en/chemie/chemie/forschung/OrgChem/ludwig/buchung/OpenIRIS/index.html>

information featured in the portal. This will ensure that the portal always contains the latest information and valid contact details. Interfaces between different systems are utilised in submitting information, in which case they are kept up to date in one location (Research Portal). Automated transfer of data from the University's infrastructure portal to the national research data repository under construction will be organised for infrastructures selected for this purpose.

Information about individual pieces of research equipment is stored in the University's equipment register. The equipment register makes it possible to access information related to equipment relevant to the functioning and shared use of research infrastructures directly from the Research Portal, and to link the information to the research infrastructures described in the portal. In such cases, maintaining information on research infrastructure components in the Research Portal will be easier, as they need to be kept up to date in the equipment register only.

UH Infrastructure portal ⁸

Key elements emerged:

- basis system: Pure by Elsevier;
- accessibility and open science;

⁸ <https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/equipments/>

- links to national level (Research.fi);
- information available via Pure API (json, xml);
- research infrastructures can be linked to projects, publications and other CRIS data;
- RI hierarchy;
- keywords (structured and free keywords).

The debate that took place during the seminar made it possible to gather some significant ideas. The experiences that were illustrated refer to institutional, local and regional level but were very useful to better understand the challenges of developing and implementing a catalogue at the Alliance level, i.e. a **common catalogue at trans-national level**, involving 11 partners and including a wide heterogeneity of infrastructures and resources, which implies a higher level of complexity. One of the main issues is related to data retention and coverage: the experiences illustrated during the seminar provided meaningful examples on this point. Another important idea that was discussed during the seminar is the need to minimize the work done locally, when building a shared catalogue: this can be achieved by **establishing an automatic dialogue** between the local catalogues and the common catalogue. In chapter 4, which focuses the technical aspects, some key inputs that emerged from the seminar have been included.

3. Lessons learned from the prototype

The prototype was designed during the first phase of the pilot action implementation to provide a concrete example of RIs catalogue in a limited perimeter. The discussions about the prototype were useful to collect inputs to draft the blueprint.

The prototype consist in a **PowerBi report** that connects to data sources consisting of excel files with data compiled by the participating institutions. A new calculated table has been added to the report data model, using the DAX formula language, to reconcile all data coming from institutional data sources in excel format.

Each data source excel file contains the following fields:

- **ID:** RI unique identifier in the local catalogue (mandatory);
- **Host Institution:** the host institution name (mandatory);
- **Name:** the short name of the RI (mandatory);
- **Type:** Equipment/Laboratory (mandatory);
- **Description:** RI description (mandatory);
- **Location:** Address, building, room where the RI is located (mandatory);
- **Contact name and contact email address** (mandatory);
- Acquisition year (optional);
- Free keywords (optional);
- Open access (Y/N) (optional);
- Services provided (Y/N) (optional);
- Web site URL (optional);

The discussion about the prototype resulted into additional areas of consideration:

- a possible **extension of the data set** with other attributes (e.g. the RI image url);
- a more accurate **definition/refinement of the data model**: which fields are mandatory, which ones are recommended, which ones are optional;
- the definition of a set of rules to ensure **data quality** for incoming data inputs (e.g. data retention and data coverage, standardization on data protocols). The main aim is ensuring the integrity and consistency of the data before it is entered into the catalogue.
- Some activities that can be performed are:
 - Data validation: data is checked to verify that it is correct, complete, and consistent with the defined rules and formats;
 - Duplicate data elimination: duplicate data is identified and removed to ensure consistency and uniqueness of information in the catalogue;
 - Data normalization: data is normalized to ensure consistency of information. This may include standardizing date formats, addresses and other fields to ensure that the data is homogeneous and easily comparable.
 - Missing or inconsistent data check: the presence of missing data or inconsistencies in required fields is verified.
 - The connection of the prototype data model to up-to-date data sources.

4. Recommendations for a future common catalogue (architecture, system, taxonomy)

Scope

The purpose of this blueprint is to provide guidelines for the development of an **information technology platform to manage a common catalogue of research infrastructures across Una Europa institutions**. This platform aims to provide a **unified system for managing research infrastructure data**, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities.

Catalogue design

The catalogue can be designed with the following considerations in mind:

- Scalability: The platform should be able to accommodate many institutions and research infrastructure data.
- Security: The platform should ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the stored data.
- Accessibility: The platform should be accessible to public and authorized users from any location and device.
- Interoperability: The platform should be able to interact with other systems and data sources as needed.
- Usability: The platform should be easy to use and navigate for all users.

Catalogue features

The following features should/could be included in the catalogue:

- User management: The platform should allow for the creation and management of user accounts with varying levels of access and permissions.
- Research infrastructure catalogue: The platform should allow for the creation and management of a catalogue of research infrastructures, including metadata such as name, location, description, and availability.
- Search and filter: The platform should allow users to search and filter the catalogue based on various criteria (key word, taxonomy based).
- Reporting and analytics: The platform should provide reporting and analytics capabilities, such as usage statistics and data visualization.
- Integration: The platform should allow for integration with other systems and data sources as needed.

Development Process: Setting up, data collection and maintenance

The development process for the catalogue should follow these steps:

- Requirements gathering: Collect and document the functional and non-functional requirements for the platform, including user stories and acceptance criteria.
- Design: Develop the high-level design of the platform, including the architecture, data model, and user interface design.
- Implementation: Develop the platform using an iterative and incremental development process, including testing and quality assurance.
- Deployment: Deploy the platform to a production environment and perform final testing and quality assurance.
- Maintenance: Provide ongoing maintenance and support for the platform, including bug fixes and feature enhancements.

This is a list of the main information systems⁹ mentioned during the workshops:

System/Platform	Short description	Main features and benefits
Vivo	VIVO is member-supported, open source software and an ontology for representing scholarship.	Free open source software; customizable; can represent, showcase, and share all types of scholarly metadata; using the standard CERIF ¹⁰
Elsevier Pure	Pure brings information from all your data sources onto a single, intelligent and secure platform	All-inclusive research overviews; make scientific results easily accessible and comply with common standards
Openiris.io	Open IRIS is a free platform to enable resource discovery and sharing	Enables sharing of state of the art resources across labs or organizations; see resources within or across organizations that are available for use; Define and enforce policies for resource usage, with statistics and invoicing

⁹ IT platform/system.

¹⁰ The Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) is the comprehensive information model for the domain of scientific research. It is intended to support interchange of research information between and with CRISs. Among other use-cases, the OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers are based upon it.

To guide the selection of the information system/IT Platform for the implementation of the common catalogue, a comprehensive evaluation is required, including a technical assessment, a cost-benefit analysis, a consideration of resource availability (in terms of personnel and economic resources), a sustainability assessment of maintenance support and feature enhancements.

A first list of taxonomies and dictionaries¹¹ has been proposed:

Taxonomy/Dictionary	Description	Url
CPV	The CPV establishes a single classification system for public procurement aimed at standardising the references used by contracting authorities and entities to describe the subject of procurement contracts.	https://simap.ted.europa.eu/web/simap/cpv
ERC Evaluation Panels and Keywords	ERC panels cover all fields of research in three domains: Physical Sciences and Engineering (PE), Life Sciences (LS), and Social Sciences and Humanities (SH). The list of keywords and descriptors associated to each panel is indicative and not exhaustive. Applications are welcomed from all fields and disciplines even if not specifically mentioned under a given panel.	https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_Panel_structure_2021_2022.pdf
ESFRI	ESFRI Thematic Areas	https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/landscape-analysis/section-1/
MERIL	MERIL RI Categories	https://portal.meril.eu/meril/downloadFile?uuid=3d7e6427-b311-45c0-bae5-6526b5376582&name=List_of_MERIL_RI_Categories.pdf

These suggested global taxonomies must align to the existing (institutional) ones or at least a mapping between the different schemes should be provided.

¹¹ Taxonomies and dictionaries are intended as classification schemes.

5. Guidelines to develop a new catalogue of infrastructures at institutional level

This section includes inputs for the institutions that currently do not have a catalogue of research infrastructures (UJ, Paris 1, Unibo) and are willing to develop a new one. The proposed elements are coherent with the features of the common catalogue proposed in this document, so as to ease the future interoperability and connection.

The first step is to **identify the research infrastructures** existing at the institution and **classify** them according to their function, research area/field, etc. The next step is to create a **database** listing the University's research infrastructures, with a detailed description, contact information, access methods, usage policies and, possibly, rates and booking procedures. A **standard format** on the necessary information on research infrastructures included in the catalogue should be adopted, to ensure that the information is complete and consistent. It is proposed to refer to a **data model based on the CERIF standard**, and to manage at least the attributes of the infrastructures that have been identified as mandatory for the common catalogue data set. Finally, an **application interface** to allow connection to the shared catalogue needs to be developed.

The catalogue should be regularly updated by the institution to ensure that the **information is up-to-date, relevant and accurate**. It is also important to **promote the catalogue** among the academic and scientific community, through for example publication on the university portal, communication actions and organization of dedicated events. A last step is to **promote new collaborations** between researchers and research infrastructures **facilitating access** to research infrastructures and encouraging the sharing of knowledge and skills.

Inputs on the **institutional perspectives** of JU, Paris 1 and Unibo were collected during the pilot and are summarized below.

Jagiellonian University

The catalogue of research infrastructures will be part of a wider information management system at the Jagiellonian University (system CRIS). From the perspective of Jagiellonian University, the **listing of research infrastructures should be integrated into a more comprehensive knowledge system** and the common research infrastructure catalogue is a first step to do that. Presently Jagiellonian University does not have a catalogue mapping such infrastructure, so in the future, when such catalogue will be created, it could probably adjust to systems chosen by the partners.

Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne

From the perspective of Paris 1 there is no interest to develop only the research infrastructure catalogue: **the listing of research infrastructures should be a part of a broader knowledge system** (institutional knowledge graph) as it is the case of Helsinki University. Developing an institutional knowledge system is more ambitious, but also more sustainable as the data describing the research are inherently linked data and should be developed together.

At this stage, Paris 1 is interested in comparing data systems for interoperability of data between member universities and searching for sustainable solutions.

University of Bologna

Improving the quality of Research infrastructures and maximizing their shared use is part of the strategic objectives set by the governance for 2027. In this view, the development of an institutional catalogue is one of the first step to be taken and University of Bologna implemented the first attempt in 2022 with a first dataset. The **knowledge of other systems already in use** in the other Una Europa universities and the **technical requirements** for the development of a common catalogue is a **great opportunity to accelerate the institutional processes** and to create a catalogue that will be immediately interoperable with the prospective Una.Resin common catalogue.

6. Future improvement: a services portal for Una Europa infrastructures

A possible future improvement of the common catalogue concerns the creation of **advanced features** that allow the dissemination of information, both at local and transnational level, and the **development of additional services** related to RIs.

The features that can be considered are the following:

- **Ensure the contact information of individual researchers requesting to get access to RI.** It is necessary to collect and verify the contact information of the user requesting access to the research infrastructure, in order to be able to provide assistance and support, ensuring effective and reliable communication.
- **Link to registration system (to use the facility) in the RI digital catalogue.** A link within the digital catalogue of RIs can allow users to easily access the registration and booking system necessary to use the facilities or services offered by the infrastructure.
- **Technical support.** A technical support system that allows researchers to request technical assistance for the use of research infrastructures and to report technical problems.
- **User training.** An online training system that allows researchers to access guides and useful material on the use of research infrastructures.
- **Notifications and alerts system.** A system of notifications and alerts that allows researchers to receive updated information on research infrastructures, ongoing projects, etc.

Two further features have been discussed, that imply a more complex scenario:

- Develop a link to an online catalogue where the **expertise of the research teams** from Una Europa universities and their **transferable research results** would be available.¹² Catalogues concerning research teams, transferable research results and RIs could be indexed in a **general platform**, i.e. a comprehensive catalogue (it could be called for instance “UnaNetworking”) useful for Una Europa researchers, for the external academic and non-academic stakeholders as well as for the general public. It could be a useful tool

¹² Research groups are group of researchers belonging to a university and focusing on one or more research topics. Transferable research activities are activities carried out by research groups (spin-off, commercialized research products, consulting services) that may be of interest to industry and society in general. Examples: <https://www.fu-berlin.de/en/sites/profund/gruendungsservice/betreute-aktuelle-Gruendungsvorhaben/index.html>
<https://www.ucm.es/otrien/complutransfer-diagnosis-of-hereditary-pathology-in-the-canine-and-feline-species>
 Example of an existing catalogue: <https://www.ucm.es/otrien/complutransfer>

to promote collaboration between researchers, since it would provide an easy way to search for potential partners for European projects, to find researchers with similar interests, to explore researchers from other disciplines studying similar topics. In addition, this catalogue could be disseminated towards citizens (promoting awareness about research results) and industry (disseminating transferable research results that can be commercialized, could be useful to promote research-business collaboration).

- **Develop a link between the RI identifier and publication/data outputs achieved by using the RI.** This feature would allow a correct and effective monitoring of scientific outputs of shared research infrastructures, which is crucial for several reasons: strategic planning, accountability, impact evaluation, sustainability, benchmarking, adaptation to changing research needs etc. By providing insights to make informed decisions, this monitoring process contributes not only to the effectiveness and efficiency of the RIs' operation but also to the advancement of research and innovation¹³. The proposed feature would also allow to **link the RI identifier and other infrastructure initiatives at different levels** (ESFRI, national, regional and institutional levels). The connection between the research infrastructure identifier and other infrastructure mapping initiatives at different levels would allow for the creation of a network of connections between the different equipment.

A general recommendation stemming from the pilot action regards the **development a universal Persistent Identifier (PID) for research infrastructures**, that would have positive impacts on linking RI and publication/data/outputs. The Flemish Department of Economy, Science and Innovation (EWI) coordinating the FRIS database has developed such identifier. During the implementation of the pilot action, it emerged that a universal RI PID could be very useful for many reasons (the same reasons that led to the development of the DOI for publications) but it seems that no University is in the process of developing it. The best practice developed by FRIS is active at the regional level and mostly related to regional funding. What Una Europa could do is to recommend it to EU and sponsor its adoption.

- ¹³ The University of Bologna is currently implementing a service with Elsevier to use their publication database and a dedicated AI tool with the objective to get quantitative data on the scientific output (i.e. number of publications per infrastructure) of each equipment listed in Unibo draft catalogue/dataset. If a RI Persistent Identifier could be used, this process would be much easier and probably no AI would be required.

7. Next steps

To set up the common RIs catalogue, Una Europa must ensure the following steps:

- Have a **clear commitment by the governance** of the Alliance members thereby guaranteeing a long-term engagement of the individual institutions to work together on the development of a common catalogue of RIs, based on an accurate assessment of the resources available at institutional level (in terms of personnel, budget and infrastructures).
- Continue the **exploration of best practices and experiences** of other alliances and projects, to exploit possible synergies, useful tools and lessons learnt, in order to develop the best and most sustainable solutions.
- Develop and **advanced version of this Blueprint**, as it is suggested in the shared Una Europa strategy and action plan for sharing research infrastructures (Deliverable 2.2) that should include:
 - An in-depth SWOT analysis that can help the selection of architecture, system and taxonomy to be adopted in the common catalogue (cf. Chapter 4).
 - The definition of a detailed project for setting up the digital catalogue and the required operation, with an adequate budget (internal and external resources) for the development and management of the such catalogue, which considers the expenses for catalogue creation, continuous updating, promotion of the catalogue and training and assistance to users.
 - The analysis of potential financial risks associated with the project, such as decreased funding, increased maintenance costs, or loss of team members. It is necessary to plan how to deal with these risks and find alternative solutions to ensure the financial viability of the project.
 - The definition of roles and responsibilities of the participating institutions, to ensure a balanced distribution of activities and efficient management of available resources across institutions.
 - The definition of processes that can ensure systematic updates of RI information through regular data collection to keep the information updated.
 - Advanced indications for the development of further services and functionalities that can lead to the development of a common online portal/platform (cf. Chapter 6)

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